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Deliverable D3.4 – Digital tools in the project website - final release

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WP3 – Set-up and Develop the Network of ERA Hubs

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COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards Era-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

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Executive summary

This deliverable, titled " D3.4 – Digital tools in the project website - final release" outlines the updated rationale and matrix starting from the initial prototype. The COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool (SA digital tool) is a digital tool that allows R&I ecosystems to test their maturity levels against a set of defined KPIs. The latter result from the feedback received from use-cases, the co-creation arenas and insights from the Co-Design Task Force. Meanwhile, the SA digital tool harmonies together other two outputs of the COOPERATE Project: the COOPERATE Toolbox and the COOPERATE Playbook.

With the goal of fostering the implementation of R&I ecosystems to fully advanced ones, the SA digital tool is flexible and adaptable to different types of R&I ecosystems and geographic areas. It stimulates an interactive, co-creative process, gathering key players of the R&I ecosystems, to agree on a balanced answer to provide when taking the SA digital tool. By doing so the understanding of the strengths and gaps to improve will be shared among the players of the R&I ecosystem, encouraging its progress.

This document, along with the "list of KPIs and related questions" (Annex I); "Privacy policy" (Annex II), "Terms of use" (Annex III) and the Appendix constitute the " D3.4 – Digital tools in the project website - final release".

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MA	Maturity Assessment
PLAYBOOK	COOPERATE Playbook
R&I	Research and Innovation
SA	Self-Assessment
TOOLBOX	COOPERATE Toolbox
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This document provides the updated rationale and KPIs selection behind the development of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool (SA digital tool). The initial reasoning and methodology are available in the Deliverable 3.3 “Digital tools in the project website - preliminary prototype”. For this reason, only the changes and/or updates will be here provided. The final version of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool – which still is a demonstrator – is available online through the COOPERATE Project website.

This deliverable will be divided into sections, tackling the main updates resulting from exchanges within the consortium, with stakeholders and from the piloting activities, highlighting the improvements and the progress made, which led to the final release of it.

Generally speaking, the aim of the SA digital tool is to allow R&I ecosystems to test their maturity level against the KPIs envisioned by the consortium, while being able to progress in their maturity path benefitting from additional materials such as the TOOLBOX and the PLAYBOOK.

In this document one will find updates on:

- The matrix of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool
- The future possible improvements
- The privacy policy and terms of use
- The questions posed for each of the lines of action
- An Appendix showing the online implementation of the SA digital tool

Overall, the work carried out within Task 3.2 is in line with the other task of the “WP3 Set-up and Develop the Network of ERA Hubs” addressing the platform development (Task 3.1), while concretising the theoretical framework developed around the concept of ERA Hubs (WP1).

2 Feedback on the prototype

The COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool aims to support and accelerate the progress of R&I ecosystems in becoming more mature. In this regard, maturity levels have been categorized into five distinct stages (see Picture 2), resonating around the Ecosystem Readiness Level concept already envisioned in the COOPERATE Deliverable “D1.1 - Initial ERA Hub Framework and KPIs” (2023). Considering this second release, the updated questions posed in the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool build on the feedback from different activities carried out with the stakeholders (see Deliverable 1.3 – “Report on the co-creation with extended CDTF”), and reactions received from the Co-Design Task Force experts, such as those of the second hands-on co-creation arena, organised on 23rd September 2024, online.

Hence, in that occasion, for example, the prototype of the SA digital tool was used to measure the maturity of two use-cases R&I ecosystems in Denmark; namely “life science” (in red) and the “sustainable technology” (in green). As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the results suggest that in both cases the R&I ecosystems are well advanced in research and innovation, while only “life science” scores 5/5 in knowledge transfer, and only “sustainable technology” is fully mature in funding. Yet, room for improvement is possible for both R&I ecosystems in the remaining lines of action, such as: talents, collaboration and governance.

Picture 1 SA results from Danish use-cases

In light of the final release of the SA digital tool and taking advantage from the tests done with the use-cases, substantial changes have been made with special regards to the questions and the possible answers. Hence, from the feedback received and the progress of the COOPERATE Project, now the SA digital tool not only is related to the TOOLBOX, but also to the PLAYBOOK. Hence the KPIs developed and used in the SA digital tool meet the hallmark from the PLAYBOOK. In other words, in its initial version

the basis against which the SA digital tool measured the maturity mainly rose from the TOOLBOX, while now the KPIs stem from feedback from the uses-cases, insights from the piloting activities, the engagement with the CDTF in the co-creation arenas, and hallmarks from the PLAYBOOK. The latter, in its turn, is related to the TOOLBOX which represents a catalogue of instruments that the R&I ecosystems can utilise to progress in their journey.

Another value of this updated version is represented by the process of taking the SA digital tool, whose intent goes beyond the facts and indicators typically found in public databases. Hence, the SA digital tool foresees an interactive and co-creative process, involving discussions among key stakeholders within the R&I ecosystem. The aim is to reach a consensual answer to each question, so that to provide a more well-rounded response about the current state of the R&I ecosystem while also fostering a shared understanding of its strengths and weaknesses.

Overall, building on the feedback and comments received on the first prototype, this release shows how the SA digital tool not only encompasses different aspects and outputs of the COOPERATE Project harmonising them in one single digital tool, but also it stimulates co-creative process among key players of the R&I ecosystem.

3 Updated matrix

The matrix proposed in the initial prototype resonated around the Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL), and the related 1-5 scale which refers to:

- 0≥1 = Absence
- 1.1≥2 = Emergence
- 2.1≥3 = Development
- 3.1≥4 = Diffusion
- 4.1≥5 = Saturation¹

The reference to the ERL is also confirmed in the final release of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool, as well as the possibility of measuring the single line of action separately from to the whole ecosystems. More in details, the single lines of action will be measured on a 0-5 scale, while the overall ecosystem on a 0-35 (as shown in Table 1 below).

	LINES OF ACTIONS						
	Research	Talent	Knowledge transfer	Funding	Collaboration	Governance	Innovation
Min-Max ERL level per line	0-5	0-5	0-5	0-5	0-5	0-5	0-5
Min-Max ERL level per ecosystem	0-35						

Table 1 - ERL level per line of action and whole ecosystem

As the overall maturity level of the ecosystem results from the maturity of each line of action, the 0-35 scale is the combination of:

$$0-5 \text{ scale} * 7 \text{ lines of action} = 0-35 \text{ scale}$$

This also implies that the weight of the lines of action is equal among them. At the same time, there is no different weights among the set of KPIs measured within each line. Therefore, the basis for the calculation remains 5 as common denominator.

Even though from a general perspective, this methodology was already developed in August 2023 with the initial prototype, in this case the calculation was improved as the scoring starts from 0, differently from the prototype which $X < 1$ was not included.

¹ In Picture 2 Saturation corresponds to Collaboration

The value of the scores follows the initial concept which combines together the level of integration with the intensity of the activities. The Picture 2 below summarizes the concept with the related scores, while providing a brief additional explanation.

Picture 2 - Levels of integration and intensity

The matrix proposed in the prototype was the one below reported:

$$Lx = \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} \frac{5}{N_T} (N_{yi} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}})$$

$\frac{1}{N_{qi}}$ will result on a number between 0 and 1 since it is calculated as a percentage (1 = 100)

MATRIX LEGEND			
Lx = Line of action	N_T = Number of tools in each Lx	N_{yi} = Number of "Yes" for each tool	N_q = Number of questions for each tool

Table 2 - Initial matrix legend

The updated matrix builds on the pillars of the previous one, but instead of addressing single tools through the questions, it refers to the set of KPIs per each line of action. In addition, the N_{yi} has been updated to N_{1-5} as the answers related to each question of the KPI is measured on a 1-5 scale, following the Likert methodology. As mentioned at the beginning, KPIs are equally weighted, thus the calculation $\frac{5}{N_k}$. The weight of the answers given is proportioned through the % related to the number of possible answers per single KPI, as per the calculation $\frac{1}{N_{qi}}$. As the Likert scale is applied to all KPIs, this calculation will always be $\frac{1}{5}$. The updated matrix will thus be the following one:

$$Lx = \sum_{i=5}^{N_k} \frac{5}{N_k} (N_{1-5} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}})$$

MATRIX LEGEND UPDATED			
Lx = Line of action	N_k = Number of KPIs in each Lx	N_{1-5} = Level from 1 to 5 according to each answer given	N_q = Number of questions for each KPIs

Table 3 – Updated matrix legend

To simulate the calculation of the maturity level, the KPIs² for the line of action “Research” will be here provided:

Question	Possible answer	Demo given answer
<i>To what extent would you assess that all relevant research areas for the ERA Hub are covered by universities/RTOs in the ecosystem?</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	3-To a moderate extent
<i>How would you assess the production of peer-reviewed publications in the ecosystem on the relevant topic(s) for the ERA Hub?</i>	1: Very low quantity 2: Low quantity 3: Moderate quantity 4: High quantity 5: Very high quantity	1-Very low quantity
<i>How easy/difficult is it for researchers or innovators in the ecosystem to access research infrastructures*?</i>	1: Very difficult 2: Difficult 3: Neutral 4: Easy 5: Very easy	3-Neutral

Table 4 - Example of questions on the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool

This means that “Research” line of action ($L1$), has three set of KPIs (N_k), with one question (N_q) each, the logic will be the following:

- $L1 = 1-5$ ERL
- N_k1 = evaluated 1-5 ERL but it weights 1,6 in total, meaning that 1,6 pt = 5 ERL
 - Q1 = Response “to a moderate extent” - 3
- N_k2 = evaluated 1-5 ERL but it weights 1,6 in total, meaning that 1,6 pt = 5 ELR
 - Q1 = Response “very low quality” - 1
- N_k3 = evaluated 1-5 ERL but it weights 1,6 in total, meaning that 1,6 pt = 5 ELR
 - Q1 = Response “neutral” - 3
- Based on these demo responses the result will be as follow:

$$Lx = \sum_{i=5}^{N_k} \frac{5}{N_k} (N_{1-5} \times \frac{1}{N_q})$$

$$Lx = \frac{5}{3} \left(3 \times \frac{1}{5} \right) + \frac{5}{3} \left(1 \times \frac{1}{5} \right) + \frac{5}{3} \left(3 \times \frac{1}{5} \right)$$

² List of all KPIs and related questions is available in Annex I

$$Lx = \frac{5}{3} (0,6) + \frac{5}{3} (0,2) + \frac{5}{3} (0,6)$$

$$Lx = 1,66 \times 0,6 + 1,66 \times 0,2 + 1,66 \times 0,6$$

$$Lx = 1 + 0,33 + 1$$

$$Lx = 2,33$$

In this case, the $L1$ ERL corresponds to 2,33 placing the overall line under the “development” level. Please note that in the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool questionnaire, the results will be rounded down +/-0,5; thus the $Lx = 2,33$ is adjusted to 2,30.

As a matter of clarity, the correlation between the ERL and the points given to each N_k , is reported below:

ERL LEVEL – INNOVATION	POINTS CORRISPONDANCE TO THE KPIS (5 pt = 5 ERL)
• 1 = Absence	• 0.00 ≥ 1.00 = Absence
• 2 = Emergency	• 1.10 ≥ 2.00 = Emergency
• 3 = Development	• 2.10 ≥ 3.00 = Development
• 4 = Diffusion	• 3.10 ≥ 4.00 = Diffusion
• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 ≥ 5.00 = Saturation (*Collaboration)

Table 5 - ERL level and KPIS correspondence

Based on that, the ERL of the whole ecosystem results from the total of the ERL reached by single Lx . Translated into the matrix, the whole ERL = $L1 + L2 + L3 + L4 + L5 + L6 + L7$. Assuming that the overall level of the whole ecosystem is 16,30 (2,30x7) the ecosystem will be considered under the “development” level.

Based on the results obtained through the questions of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool, a radar graph will be provided³, summarising and visualising the maturity level per each line of action: the closer to the centre the lower degree of maturity. Finally, according to the single lines of action, suggested tools are provided, allowing the R&I ecosystem to progress in their path in becoming more advanced.

The final version of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool will provide:

- Registration page

³ See in the Appendix the “Results Page”

- Instruction page
- Questions per lines of action
- Results page with tools
- Link to the COOPERATE Toolbox

The next chapter provides possible improvements foreseen for a further future development, in light of the advanced done so far in the “demonstrator phase”.

4 Room for future improvement

Considering that the SA digital tool is – at this stage – still a demonstrator and following the theoretical discourse, both the lines of actions and the KPIs equally weighted. Nonetheless, a possible improvement for the future would be to develop a matrix that can, if required by the methodology of the concept, process data for KPIs with different weights. In addition, a further implementation could be done in relation to the tools provided. Hence, each tool foresees a recommended maturity level in different lines of action to elevate one or more lines. In concrete, the tool “Centres of excellence”, for example, elevates three lines of actions – namely research, funding and innovation – while recommending the following maturity levels to fully benefit from it: research (3), talent (3), funding (3), innovation (2), collaboration (4). The matrix proposed for this demonstrator does not include the “*if*” parameter, from which it follows that the tool “centres of excellence” should be suggested only *if* the recommended maturity per line(s) of actions have been achieved. At this stage, since the recommended maturity in the TOOLBOX may also be improved, and the intention now is to allow R&I ecosystems to navigate the full catalogue without being directed to some specific tools, this functionality has not been integrated. Nonetheless, this may be a possible step to take in the future.

All in all, the added value of the SA digital tool may be also seen in this aspect: it matches together the different outputs of the COOPERATE Project, by concretising the definition and the framework into an accessible online questionnaire that R&I ecosystems can benefit from to assess their level of maturity.

5 Privacy policy and terms of use

For the final release, users are required to register to the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool to access the questionnaire. The data needed are the following ones:

- Name and surname
- Email address
- Employment
- City/country and post code
- Location

The data are processed according to the “general conditions – terms of use”; the “privacy policy” and the “cookies” policy. Those data are available in the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool at the following address <https://cooperate.stamtech.dev/> . The data controller is the company STAM S.r.l., with registered office in Genoa (Italy), Via Pareto 8r A – 16129, in relation to the " COOrdinating and

Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE)" project Grant Agreement number 101095017.

Following the Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), the user has the right to:

- Access personal data (Article 15 GDPR)
- Obtain the rectification of inaccurate data (Article 16 GDPR) and the deletion of data (Article 17 GDPR)
- Obtain the restriction of processing (Article 18 GDPR)
- Request and obtain from the Controller personal data in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format (Article 20 GDPR)
- Object to the processing at any time and also in the case of processing for direct marketing purposes (Article 21 GDPR)
- Oppose automated decision-making relating to natural persons, including profiling (Article 21 GDPR)
- Revoke consent at any time, limited to cases where the processing is based on your consent, without affecting the lawfulness of the processing based on the consent given before revocation

In addition, pursuant to Articles 37 et seq. of the Regulation, a direct email account of the Data Protection Officer (DPO), located at the Controller's registered office, has been provided for contacts: privacy@stamtech.com. Annex II – Privacy policy and Annex III – Terms of use provide the full version of the “privacy policy” and “terms of use”.

6 Conclusions

The final version of the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool introduces an update in the matrix, shifting from a simple yes/no format to a more detailed 1-5 scale in the answers. This change better reflects the Key Performance Indicators against which assessing the maturity of the R&I ecosystems. The questions of the KPIs built on co-creation arenas, feedback from use-cases, piloting activities, and hallmark of the PLAYBOOK, going beyond the initial drafting which was mainly developed from the TOOLBOX.

Besides, the updated version envisions a co-creative process, bringing together the key players of the R&I ecosystem to address the questions in a collaboratively way. This collective approach ensures that the answers provided are as comprehensive as possible and accurately represent the R&I ecosystem.

Yet, one area for improvement in the SA digital tool is the ability to assign different weights to the KPIs and action lines. This adjustment would better reflect the relative importance of each aspect and allow for more targeted insights. Furthermore, in the future an advanced version of the SA digital tool may also recommend specific tools based on the achieved level and the desired maturity level for each tool, offering tailored guidance for continue development.

Overall, the added value of the assessment lays in the fact that it brings together the various outputs of the COOPERATE project by translating the definition and framework into an easily accessible online questionnaire, enabling R&I ecosystems to assess their level of maturity, and progress in their journey.

A. Annex I – List of KPIs and related questions

a. Research

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
To what extent would you assess that all relevant research areas for the ERA Hub are covered by universities/RTOs in the ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) are public or private non-profit organisations whose core mission is to produce, combine and bridge various types of knowledge, skills, and infrastructures to deliver a range of research and development activities in collaboration with public and industrial partners of all sizes⁴. • Own assessment of coverage in research of those areas that are relevant for the ERA Hub, as opposed to gaps in knowledge or knowhow for the development of the ERA Hub.
How would you assess the production of peer-reviewed publications in the ecosystem on the relevant topic(s) for the ERA Hub?	1: Very low quantity 2: Low quantity 3: Moderate quantity 4: High quantity 5: Very high quantity	Own assessment of quantity and quality (e.g., citation rates, level of novelty), specific to the (sub)field(s) and relative to the size of the ERA Hub and in terms of specialisation compared to other research areas or other regions.
How easy/difficult is it for researchers or innovators in the ecosystem to access research infrastructures *?	1: Very difficult 2: Difficult 3: Neutral 4: Easy 5: Very easy	<p>*Research Infrastructures are major instruments, resources, or service facilities for research in all disciplines. They include major scientific equipment or sets of instruments; collections, archives or scientific data; computing systems and communication networks; any other research and innovation infrastructure of a unique nature which is open to external users.</p> <p>These infrastructures differ from other research-related entities in the fact that they tend to have at least national significance and have a long life (e.g., more than ten years). Access to them and use of their services and equipment is usually open and based on research excellence standards. The costs of their development and construction are so high that they require substantial national public funds⁵.</p>

⁴ <https://www.earto.eu/about-rtos/>

⁵ For instance: <https://erf-aisbl.eu/members/>

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures_en

b. Talent

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
Would you assess that there are sufficient training programmes for diverse R&I profiles in the ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Diverse R&I profiles could include e.g., research management, data management, innovation and valorisation skills, tech transfer skills, ...</i> • <i>Sufficiency can refer to e.g., number of training possibilities, topics, diversity, quality...</i>
Would you assess that there are sufficient training programmes for entrepreneurship and knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<i>Sufficiency can refer to e.g., number of training possibilities, topics, diversity, quality...</i>
To what extent is the brain drain an issue in/for the ecosystem?	1: To a very high extent – Entirely 2: To a high extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a low extent 5: Not at all - to a very low extent	
How successful is the ecosystem in attracting and retaining talent in the ecosystem?	1: Not successful 2: Somewhat successful 3: Moderately successful 4: Considerably successful 5: Very successful	<i>Talent does not only include researchers, but also other RTI profiles.</i>
How would you assess the impact of the following elements on the attractiveness of the ecosystem for RTI profiles?		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working conditions (including salaries) 	1: Strong negative impact 2: Small negative impact 3: No impact 4: Small positive impact 5: Strong positive impact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Career prospects / diversity of career opportunities 	1: Strong negative impact 2: Small negative impact 3: No impact 4: Small positive impact 5: Strong positive impact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of living 	1: Strong negative impact 2: Small negative impact 3: No impact 4: Small positive impact 5: Strong positive impact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of education and childcare 	1: Strong negative impact	

	2: Small negative impact 3: No impact 4: Small positive impact 5: Strong positive impact	
To what extent do researchers find it difficult/easy to work outside academia in the ecosystem?	1: Very difficult 2: Difficult 3: Neutral 4: Easy 5: Very easy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E.g., in companies, policy organisations, social organisations, ... • E.g., in terms of finding a position, being accepted for a position, having the right (transversal) skills...

c. Knowledge transfer

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
How would you assess the extent to which different actors in the ecosystem are open to new ideas and solutions (e.g., to experiment or introduce change)?		
<i>Companies</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
<i>Social organisations</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
<i>Public authorities</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
<i>Universities</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	

RTOs

- 1: Not at all - to a very low extent
- 2: To a low extent
- 3: To a moderate extent
- 4: To a high extent
- 5: To a very high extent - Entirely

Are there enough knowledge sharing infrastructures in the ecosystem?

- 1: Not at all
- 2: To some extent
- 3: To a moderate extent
- 4: To a considerable extent
- 5: To a high extent

E.g., maker spaces, co-working spaces, knowledge sharing platforms...

To what extent do actors in the ecosystem use knowledge sharing infrastructures?

- 1: Not at all
- 2: To some extent
- 3: To a moderate extent
- 4: To a considerable extent
- 5: To a high extent

Are there sufficient academia-industry programmes for R&I available in the ecosystem?

- 1: Not at all
- 2: To some extent
- 3: To a moderate extent
- 4: To a considerable extent
- 5: To a high extent

E.g., internships, mentorships and job placement opportunities

To what extent do actors in the ecosystem use academia-industry programmes for R&I?

- 1: Not at all
- 2: To some extent
- 3: To a moderate extent
- 4: To a considerable extent
- 5: To a high extent

To what extent have informal knowledge sharing events been organised in the ecosystem in the last year?

- 1: Not at all
- 2: To some extent
- 3: To a moderate extent
- 4: To a considerable extent
- 5: To a high extent

E.g., workshops, hackathons...

How would you assess the attendance rates of these informal knowledge sharing events?

- 1: Very low
- 2: Low
- 3: Moderate
- 4: High
- 5: Very high

d. Funding

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
To what extent are the ecosystem needs met in terms of funding for the following purposes?		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>In terms of total amount, amount per project or grant, period, focus, ...</i> • <i>Funding refers to funding at all levels, available to the ecosystem (actors).</i>
• <i>Basic research</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
• <i>PoC, testing and development,</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
• <i>Startup creation</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
• <i>Upscaling, commercialisation...</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
To what extent is relevant funding for the following purposes known in the ecosystem?		<i>Funding refers to funding at all levels, available to the ecosystem (actors).</i>
• <i>Basic research</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
• <i>PoC, testing and development...</i>	1: Not at all - to a very low extent	

2: To a low extent
3: To a moderate extent
4: To a high extent
5: To a very high extent -
Entirely

- *Upscaling, commercialisation...*

1: Not at all - to a very low
extent
2: To a low extent
3: To a moderate extent
4: To a high extent
5: To a very high extent -
Entirely

- *Startup creation*

1: Not at all - to a very low
extent
2: To a low extent
3: To a moderate extent
4: To a high extent
5: To a very high extent -
Entirely

e. Collaboration

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
To what extent is transparency of the ecosystem's organisation, network and accessibility supported by formal initiatives ?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Transparency in terms of access point, links, involvement of actors, ...</i> • <i>Formal initiatives such as key account managers, access points e.g., website or online platform, network or cluster organisation...</i>
How easy/difficult is it for newcomers to engage in collaboration in the ecosystem?	1: Very difficult 2: Difficult 3: Neutral 4: Easy 5: Very easy	
Can you indicate which actors are actively collaborating in your ecosystem?	1: Universities 2: + RTOs 3: + Public Authorities 4: + Companies and/or social organisations 5: + Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>This question focuses on the representation of the different types of actors of the quadruple helix in the ecosystem.</i> • <i>Assuming that an ecosystem would typically build up in this order of including different types of actors (from 1 to 5).</i>
To what extent would you assess that all relevant actors are active partners in the ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<i>This question focuses on the representation of all relevant individual actors in the ecosystem.</i>
How would you describe the interaction between the actors in the ecosystem?	1: There is no/hardly any interaction between actors 2: There is communication and information exchange between actors 3: There is alignment of activities for mutual benefits and achievement of complementary goals between actors 4: There is coordination of activities by actors to achieve compatible goals 5: There are joint activities based on a joint strategy, joint responsibilities and joint goals	
To what extent have the actors in the ecosystem developed a shared vision on R&I priorities ?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
To what extent have the actors in the ecosystem developed a shared vision on communication ?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent	

	3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
Is there a monitoring/evaluation system of the ecosystem in place?	1: No 2: Yes, but rather rudimentary 3: Yes, fairly well developed and implemented 4: Yes, considerably well developed and implemented 5: Yes, strongly developed and implemented	<i>E.g., to track progress in the development of the ecosystem, progress and performance of the collaboration in the ecosystem...</i>
Is the ecosystem sufficiently visible towards potential partners, policy makers, the broader public...?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<i>E.g., through joint communication and outreach channels such as websites, social networks, local media outlets, community newsletters...</i>

f. Governance

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
To what extent have the actors in the ecosystem developed a shared vision on governance ?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
To what extent is there a clear division of roles and responsibilities between the actors involved in the ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
Do the actors in the ecosystem work together under formalised agreements to carry out activities?	1: Never 2: Rarely 3: Sometimes 4: Regularly 5: (Very) often	<i>E.g., Memorandum of Understanding, long-term contracts...</i>
To what extent are national/regional policy makers committed to fostering progress in R&I in the ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	
To what extent is the regulatory environment facilitating the development of the R&I ecosystem?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>E.g., administrative requirements, regulations, policies...</i> • <i>Taking into account both the national and regional level (if applicable).</i>

g. Innovation

SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS	RESPONSE OPTIONS	EXPLANATION
How would you rate the ecosystem's output in terms of number of innovative products and services offered to users ?	1: Very low 2: Low 3: Moderate 4: High 5: Very high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Referring to innovative products and services that are close/ready to be brought to the users. • Users including e.g., market, policy makers, social organisations, citizens... • Can be used to benchmark with oneself over time.
To what extent do entrepreneurs have specific infrastructure and support programmes available in the ecosystem to develop their ideas/projects?	1: Not at all - to a very low extent 2: To a low extent 3: To a moderate extent 4: To a high extent 5: To a very high extent - Entirely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This question generally aims to assess if startups have access to the support they need to develop. • Support may include e.g., availability of incubators, accelerators, living labs, mentorships...
How would you assess the level of activity of innovation intermediaries in the ecosystem?	1: Very low 2: Low 3: Moderate 4: High 5: Very high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of activity referring to e.g., organisation of/participation in events and support tools, number of users/members/contacts... • Innovation intermediaries including e.g., Tech Transfer Offices, Knowledge Transfer Offices, cluster organizations...
How active are venture capitalist or business angel investors in the ecosystem?	1: Not active at all 2: Somewhat active 3: Moderately active 4: Active 5: Very active	

B. Annex II – Privacy policy

Dear User,

The personal data you provide by filling in the registration form on the self-assessment digital tool (e.g., "account registration," "profile modification," "employee modification") will be processed, including by means of computerised and electronic tools, by STAM S.r.l. in its capacity as Data Controller, in relation to the "COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE)" project Grant Agreement number 101095017. The information referred to in Article 13 Regulation (EU) 2016/679 or GDPR is provided below.

1. Data Controller

The company STAM S.r.l., with registered office in Genoa (Italy), Via Pareto 8r A - 16129, is the Data Controller (hereinafter referred to as "the Data Controller").

2. Type of Data Being Processed

The Controller will process the following personal data, including but not limited to:

- Name and surname
- Email address
- City/country and post code
- Employment company/university/organisation
- Location

3. Purpose of the Processing

Personal data will be processed by the Data Controller:

1. For the creation and management of your account and profile which will be visible to all the subscribers of the self-assessment digital tool
2. To enable you to benefit from the services reserved for registered users
3. To respond to your enquiries
4. For the handling of disputes and litigation

4. Legal Basis for Processing

The legal basis justifying the aforementioned processing in relation to the purposes:

1. Legitimate interest of the Controller in providing the information you requested balanced against your interest in receiving it (purpose 1)
2. Performance of a project-related public interest task (purpose 2)
3. Legitimate interest of the Controller in protecting its rights (purpose 3)

5. Recipients of Personal Data

Your data will be processed by:

- Employees and collaborators of the Data Controller, defined as "Authorised Persons" of the processing, if the task of such employees requires it. Each processor is specifically identified, authorised, and trained, and acts on the basis of specific instructions provided by the Company regarding the purposes and methods of processing.
-
- The data you provide for the creation of your profile account (name, surname, organisation, location) may be visible to other Users registered on the Platform.

6. Data Collection and Consequences of Failure to Provide Data

The submission of your personal data marked with an asterisk (*) is necessary for the creation of your account and to enable you to take advantage of the features provided by the self-assessment digital tool for registered Users; failure to provide them will have no consequence other than to prevent registration on the self-assessment digital tool. The provision of your personal data not marked with an asterisk (*) is optional.

7. Personal Data Retention Period

Your data will be stored until you decide to delete your account or once two years have passed following the end of the COOPERATE project.

8. Data Protection Officer (DPO)

The Data Protection Officer (DPO), pursuant to Articles 37 et seq. of the Regulation, located at the Controller's registered office, can be contacted at: privacy@stamtech.com

9. Data Transfer Abroad

Data are not transferred to non-EU countries.

10. Rights of the Data Subject

The Data Controller informs you that you have the right, within the limits prescribed by Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), to:

- Access personal data (Article 15 GDPR)
- Obtain the rectification of inaccurate data (Article 16 GDPR) and the deletion of data (Article 17 GDPR)
- Obtain the restriction of processing (Article 18 GDPR)
- Request and obtain from the Controller personal data in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format (Article 20 GDPR)
- Object to the processing at any time and also in the case of processing for direct marketing purposes (Article 21 GDPR)
- Oppose automated decision-making relating to natural persons, including profiling (Article 21 GDPR)
- Revoke consent at any time, limited to cases where the processing is based on your consent, without affecting the lawfulness of the processing based on the consent given before revocation

The aforementioned rights may be exercised upon request to be sent to the dedicated email address privacy@stamtech.com or by writing to STAM S.r.l., Via Pareto 8r A - 16129 - Genoa (Italy).

11. Right to Complain

If you believe that the processing of your personal data is in breach of the provisions of the GDPR, you have the right to make a complaint to the lead supervisory authority "Office of the Privacy Guarantor" (by email: garante@gdpd.it, or by post, to the office in Rome (Italy), Piazza Venezia 11 Scala B, post code 00187) or to your local supervisory authority as provided for in Article 77 of the GDPR, or to bring an action before the appropriate courts (Article 79 of GDPR).

C. Annex III – Terms of use

GENERAL CONDITIONS - TERMS OF USE

Foreword

This document entitled "General Terms and Conditions - Terms of Use" constitutes the Regulation of the COOPERATE self-assessment digital tool and sets out the rights and responsibilities of the User when using the services offered. By using the services via the self-assessment digital tool or even only by browsing the Site, the User undertakes to comply with these General Terms and Conditions. The site <https://cooperate.stamtech.dev/> is a technological self-assessment digital tool designed, managed and owned by the company STAM S.r.l., in the person of its pro tempore legal representative, with registered office in Genoa (Italy), Via Pareto 8r A - 16129 (hereinafter also referred to as "Service Provider" or "Manager"). The provisions of these Regulations, together with the applicable legal provisions, exclusively define the rights and obligations of the User, as well as the rights, obligations and scope of liability of the Service Provider. Browsing the site and using the self-assessment digital tool implies acknowledgement and full acceptance of these General Terms and Conditions. The foreword forms an integral part of this document.

1) General provisions

1. Within the framework of the project funded by the European Commission and called " COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE)" project Grant Agreement number 101095017", the main purpose of the self-assessment digital tool is to facilitate the registered users to assess the level of maturity of their ecosystems, against the ERA Hub indicators identified within COOPERATE Project.
2. Use of the self-assessment digital tool may only take place under the terms and conditions set out in the Regulations.
3. All intellectual property rights to the platform, in particular source code, texts, navigation solutions, selection and layout of the content presented, verbal and graphic logos, trademarks, interactive applications, photos, and forms are the property of the Manager.
4. Any modification, copying, distribution, communication, dissemination or transfer for any reason whatsoever of the aforementioned materials and any other activity that infringes the rights of the Manager is not permitted, except on the basis of special authorisation granted by the same.
5. The service provider reserves the right to store "cookies" on the User's devices to facilitate the User's navigation and for the proper functioning of the site. For the purposes of the applicable legislation, the cookie policy is specified in the "Privacy and Cookie Policy" document published on the site.

2) Managing access credentials - Rules for using the Platform

- 1 To use all the features offered by the platform, it is necessary to create an account after registration; the information provided must therefore be true, complete and accurate. The User is solely responsible for actions performed through their account, such as taking the self-assessment questionnaire. The User is responsible for any improper activity that occurs on the platform due to the User's failure to keep their access credentials confidential.
- 2 The Manager assumes no liability to Users in relation to any damage that may be caused to them as a result of unauthorised access - by third parties - to the self-assessment digital tool due to the User's failure to safeguard their access credentials.
- 3 In addition to these General Terms and Conditions, the use of the services offered must comply with the laws in force and with other regulations relating to the individual services offered by the self-assessment digital tool, which are specific provisions with respect to these Regulations; in particular, the User using the self-assessment digital tool is obliged to:
 - refrain from any act that may hinder or interrupt the operation of the site or make it difficult for other users to use it;
 - not interfere with or damage the site/ self-assessment digital tool or the service offered through the use of, but not limited to, viruses, cancelbots, trojans, malicious code, denial-of-service attacks, backdoors, IP spoofing, counterfeit routing;
 - not use the self-assessment digital tool with the intention of "spamming";
 - alter and/or modify the features offered by the self-assessment digital tool;
 - not perform any act that may damage the self-assessment digital tool Manager's image and/or reputation;

- provide real personal data; in this regard, it is hereby specified that the creation of false accounts, the use of personal data of other persons and/or Users as one's own data, and the sharing of one's own accounts with other persons is prohibited;
 - respect the intellectual property rights and rights arising from the registration of other Users/Companies' inventions, patents, trade marks, utility and industrial models;
 - update the data submitted previously during registration and account creation;
 - take note of the amendments to these Regulations.
- 3) It is forbidden to publish text, graphic, multimedia content and materials on the self-assessment digital tool that:
- are offensive or violate national or international laws or regulations;
 - are unlawful, misleading, fraudulent, threatening, abusive, libellous, defamatory, obscene, pornographic or blasphemous; are of a sexist, political or racial character; call for racial, political, religious or sexist hatred; incite violence or the commission of offences;
 - infringe the rights of others, including intellectual and industrial property rights;
 - violate the principles of netiquette and any other activity that may expose the Manager to legal liability or cause unfair harm to others;
 - have a purpose or content detrimental to fair competition.
1. As the User is responsible for the content entered through their account, the Service Provider has the right to remove or invite moderation of content that they consider illegal or contrary to the Regulations, as well as the right to suspend the use of the platform of Users who violate these General Terms and Conditions and the regulations in force. Before proceeding with the suspension, the Manager shall send a prior notice to the User containing the reasons for the possible suspension and the possibility of making a complaint against the suspension decision. Any decision by the Manager will be substantiated.
2. The Manager is not responsible nor accepts any obligation for the content published and stored on the self-assessment digital tool by the User or for any loss or damage of such content. The Service Provider shall similarly not be liable for any errors, defamation, slander, insults, omissions, falsehoods or infringement of any rights it may detect. As a provider of interactive services, the Service Provider has no responsibility for the statements, opinions or content shared by its Users.
3. Although the Service Provider has no obligation to view and monitor published content, in the case of content that contravenes these Regulations and current legislation, the Service Provider reserves the right, at its sole discretion, to proceed with the removal, at any time and without prior notice, of content published or stored on the Platform.
- 4) The services that can be used by registering on the self-assessment digital tool and creating an account are as follows:
- the ability to take the self-assessment questionnaire
 - the possibility to download the self-assessment results
 - the ability to view data relating to companies/universities/ organisation that are registered on the Platform.
- 5) Account deletion
1. The User has the option to no longer use the services offered by the self-assessment digital tool by removing their account voluntarily.
 2. The Service Provider may delete the User's account following suspension if the requirements of Section 2.3 are not met.
 3. The company/university/ organisation account manager may notify and request that the Manager delete the account of an employee who has ceased working for the company. The deletion of the organisation's account may also be requested.
- 6) Liability exemptions of the Manager
1. With the exception of the above regulations, the liability of the Manager is excluded for:
 - any damage caused to third parties as a result of use by Users in a manner contrary to the regulations or legal provisions;

- loss of data by the User due to external or other circumstances beyond the control of the Service Provider;
 - lack of availability of the self-assessment digital tool for reasons dependent on third parties;
 - inability to access the self-assessment digital tool and interruption of some or all features caused by the need for any updates or the need to carry out maintenance activities;
 - technical problems related to accessing and using the self-assessment digital tool caused by reasons beyond the Manager's control, including those caused by unforeseeable circumstances and force majeure or by the malfunctioning of the Internet network;
 - any deletion and removal of content, blocking, suspension and deletion of accounts carried out or ordered by the Judicial Authorities and Law Enforcement Agencies for the purpose of investigating and prosecuting criminal offences.
2. The Service Provider does not guarantee the accuracy or completeness of the information, text, graphics, links or other details contained in the self-assessment digital tool. The Service Provider shall not be liable for any indirect, direct, special, incidental or consequential damages, losses or costs, including, but not limited to, damage to image, reputation or loss of business profits, business interruption, loss of data, computer failure or malfunction, or damages or penalties that may result from the use of the enclosed information.
 3. The Manager reserves the right to modify, improve and delete the functionalities of the self-assessment digital tool at any time, without this entitling Users to any form of compensation or indemnity for the simple fact that there have been modifications and deletions; as far as possible, the Manager will ensure that Users are adequately informed of the changes made to the main functionalities of the self-assessment digital tool.
 4. By virtue of the above, the User uses the services in a professional manner and the Service Provider will in no case be liable to Users and registered Companies for any type of damage, whether direct or indirect, or for any loss of income, profit, company value, damage to image and reputation, data, or use of money or for any loss or damage of any nature whatsoever resulting from or relating to the following events: business interruption of any nature whatsoever; access to or use of services; delay or inability to access or use services; pecuniary damage of any nature whatsoever resulting from the use of the self-assessment digital tool or due to any personal or financial data stored on it; errors or omissions in the published content or any other type of loss or damage suffered as a result of the use of the content or resulting in any other way from access to or use of services. The foregoing applies to loss or damage, whether due to negligence, recklessness, or wrongful acts.
- 7) Processing of personal data
- With regard to the processing of personal data, see the document published on the site, at the bottom of the account registration form and also available via this link <https://cooperate.stamtech.dev/>
- 8) Complaints and enquiries
1. Any complaints regarding the services provided or the content published by Users, as well as the way the platform operates and any requests for information, may be sent to the email address privacy@stamtech.com
 2. A properly filed complaint should contain at least the following data:
 - identification of the person making the complaint (name, surname, company/university/organisation of which the individual is an employee, email address);
 - subject of the complaint;
 - circumstances giving rise to the complaint.
 3. Complaints will be considered within 30 days of their receipt by the Manager. In the event of the need to substantiate the complaint, the time limit for considering the complaint shall run from the date of delivery, including by means of distance communication, of the last document requested or the last piece of information requested.
 4. The Manager shall examine complaints in accordance with the provisions of these Regulations.
 5. Decisions on the complaint will be made by the Manager in writing and communicated to the complainant by email.
 6. The right to enforce one's claims arising from the provision of services electronically by the Manager before the Ordinary Court may be enforced once the complaints procedure has been exhausted.
- 9) Amendment of Regulations and discontinuation of self-assessment digital tool use
1. The Service Provider reserves the right to amend these General Terms and Conditions - Terms of Use; further use of the services after the publication of the notice of changes will imply acceptance of these changes.
 2. The Service Provider may (without incurring any liability) at any time modify, suspend or discontinue in whole or in part the use of the platform or the availability of any function, database or content.

3. The Service Provider may impose restrictions or otherwise limit access to the self-assessment digital tool, in whole or in part, without prior notice or obligation, for technical or security reasons to prevent unauthorised access, loss or destruction of data, or when the Service Provider considers that any provision of this document, applicable law or regulation has been violated, resulting in the obligation to discontinue the provision of the Services.

10) Applicable law and Jurisdiction

These General Terms and Conditions shall be governed by and interpreted in accordance with Italian law. The Parties agree to submit to the exclusive jurisdiction and competence of the Court of Brussels in relation to any dispute or question arising against the Manager arising from these General Conditions.

11) Final provisions

1. The rights and obligations of the Service Provider are defined exclusively by these Regulations and the mandatory statutory provisions.
2. This document shall come into force on the day of its publication on the <https://cooperate.stamtech.dev/> website, from which day it shall apply to Users and Companies registered on the self-assessment digital tool.
3. The Manager reserves the right to assign in whole or in part any of its rights and obligations relating to the self-assessment digital tool, without the need for the consent of, or the opportunity to express any objections from, the Users.
4. The invalidity of one of the provisions of the Regulation by a decision of the competent court does not invalidate the remaining provisions of the Regulation.

UNFAIR TERMS

Pursuant to and for the purposes of Articles 1341 and 1342 of the Italian Civil Code, the following clauses are expressly accepted: paragraph 2, paragraph 4, paragraph 5, paragraph 7, paragraph 8, paragraph 9.

D. Appendix

The COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool is available at <https://cooperate.stamtech.dev/>

a. "Registration page"

The screenshot shows the registration page for the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool. The page features a large COOPERATE logo in the top right corner and a smaller version in the top left. The registration form is titled "Register" and includes the following fields:

- First name
- Last name
- Email
- Password
- Confirm password

Below the form, there is a link for "[← BACK TO SIGN IN](#)" and a blue "REGISTER" button. The background of the page is white with a network diagram consisting of grey nodes and lines.

b. "Instruction page"

Cooperate Self-Assessment
← Back

INSTRUCTION PAGE

This self-assessment questionnaire tool is meant to assess the **maturity level of R&I ecosystems**. It is structured along the **seven lines of action** identified within the COOPERATE project. The lines of action are:

- L1. Research
- L2. Talent
- L3. Knowledge transfer
- L4. Funding
- L5. Collaboration
- L6. Governance
- L7. Innovation

Results

By taking the self-assessment, applicants will be able to assess the maturity level of their R&I ecosystem **overall or by single line of action**. Based on the level reached, the "RESULTS PAGE" will automatically provide the final results, as a **radar scheme** (See example below).

ERL - SEVEN LINES

The **scoring system** reflects the following rationale:

- Single line of action (0-5)

- Overall ecosystem (0-35)

The self-assessment can be taken **multiple times**, so that the maturity level of the ecosystem can be assessed at different moments in time. The **progress of the ecosystem over time** is the main output to be achieved.

Process

The self-assessment questionnaire goes beyond facts or indicators available in public repositories. It aims to collect more in-depth information that often requires a qualitative assessment. For this reason, **the self-assessment process will be an interactive, co-creative process**, based on discussion between different actors in the ecosystem.

The idea is that a group of (for instance 4 or 5) actors, core to the ecosystem, sit together and each bring their own view on the situation and discuss the underlying reasons or patterns for each topic. By discussing the questions and trying to get to a consensual answer for each of them, the actors will be able to provide a more **balanced answer to the question on the situation as is** but also come to a **profound joint understanding of the strengths of the ecosystem and its gaps**.

The self-assessment tool will provide a **realistic view on the current maturity level** of the ecosystem and will help to create a better understanding of the **needs and possible actions** to further strengthen it.

Practical guidelines

- **Access is (only) provided to the contact person**, who is responsible for filling out the questionnaire after discussion with the core group of actors. The questionnaire can be downloaded from the website as PDF to circulate beforehand.
- All questions in the tool should be filled out by selecting **one answer option per question**.
- **Additional explanations** are provided in a paragraph below the questions, where relevant.
- The **answers and results can be saved as PDF** after filling out the questionnaire.

Start

c. Sample of "Questions per line of action"

Ⓜ

Cooperate Self-Assessment
← Back

2. Talent

4. Would you assess that there are sufficient training programmes for diverse R&I profiles in the ecosystem? *

Diverse R&I profiles could include e.g. research management, data management, innovation and valorisation skills, tech transfer skills, ... Sufficiency can refer to e.g. number of training possibilities, topics, diversity, quality...

1: Not at all - to a very low extent
2: To a low extent
3: To a moderate extent
4: To a high extent
5: To a very high extent - Entirely

1 2 3 4 5

5. Would you assess that there are sufficient training programmes for entrepreneurship and knowledge valorisation in the ecosystem? *

Sufficiency can refer to e.g. number of training possibilities, topics, diversity, quality...

1: Not at all - to a very low extent
2: To a low extent
3: To a moderate extent
4: To a high extent
5: To a very high extent - Entirely

1 2 3 4 5

6. To what extent is brain drain an issue in/for the ecosystem? *

1: To a very high extent - Entirely
2: To a high extent
3: To a moderate extent
4: To a low extent
5: Not at all - to a very low extent

1 2 3 4 5

7. How successful is the ecosystem in attracting and retaining talent in the ecosystem? *

Talent does not only include researchers, but also other RTI profiles.

1: Not successful
2: Somewhat successful
3: Moderately successful
4: Considerably successful
5: Very successful

1 2 3 4 5

8. How would you assess the impact of the following elements on the attractiveness of the ecosystem for RTI profiles? *

	1: Strong negative impact	2: Small negative impact	3: No impact	4: Small positive impact	5: Strong positive impact
Working conditions (including salaries)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Career prospects / diversity of career opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cost of living	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quality of education and childcare	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. To what extent do researchers find it difficult/easy to work outside academia in the ecosystem? *

E.g. in companies, policy organisations, social organisations, ...
E.g. in terms of finding a position, being accepted for a position, having the right (transversal) skills, ...

1: Very difficult
2: Difficult
3: Neutral
4: Easy
5: Very easy

1 2 3 4 5

Previous
Next

d. Sample of radar and R&I ecosystem score in the "Results Page"

e. Sample of scores per line of action with related tools in the "Result Page"

